

3 **Equilibrium-line altitude and temperature reconstructions during the Last**
4 **Glacial Maximum in Chirripó National Park, Costa Rica**

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15

16 **Abstract**

17 Several high areas of Central America show evidence of past glacial activity,
18 including glacial cirques, polished and striated bedrock surfaces and moraine
19 deposits. As glacial remnants, these morphologies can guide the understanding
20 of past climate conditions, such as during the Last Glacial Maximum (LGM).
21 Based on aerial imagery (1:25,000), detailed Digital Elevation Model (DEM)
22 and field geomorphic assessments, we establish paleo-equilibrium line
23 altitudes using four methods: Median Glacier Elevation (MGE), Accumulation
24 Area Ratio (AAR), Area x Altitude (AA), and Area-Altitude Balance Ratio
25 (AABR) during the LGM for the Chirripó National Park in Costa Rica. In
26 addition, we calculate the LGM paleo-temperature decrease multiplying
27 several modern atmospheric lapse rates by the equilibrium line altitude
28 depression. In addition, a Generalized Linear Model (GLM) was applied to
29 describe linkages between obtained paleoglacier areas and multiple land
30 surface para-meters such as Basin location, Analytical Hillshading, Aspect,
31 Area Surface Radiation, Diurnal Anisotropic Heating, Slope, Terrain

32 Ruggedness Index, and Wind Exposition. Our results determined thirty-one
33 paleo equilibrium line altitudes (paleo-ELAs) and a mean altitude of ~3490 m
34 a.s.l. Some of the moraines used in this study have been recently dated,
35 confirming the extension of the glaciers during LGM used to calculate the
36 ELAs. We also obtained an annual average temperature decrease of ~10.5 °C
37 applying a lapse rate of 0.65 °C/100. Moreover, Wind Exposition and Terrain
38 Ruggedness Index were the land surface parameters with greater sta-tistical
39 correlation for paleo-glacier areas. Therefore, our results provide new
40 knowledge into the reconstruction of the maximum expansion of the LGM on
41 tropical landscapes.

42

43 1. Introduction

44

45 Past fluctuations of glaciers provide key data to improve the knowledge of high-
46 altitude paleoclimate changes in the tropics (Hostetler and Clark, 2000; Alcalá-
47 Reygosa et al., 2017). To reconstruct past glacial advances, the presence of well-
48 preserved glacial deposits is essential (Lachniet and Vázquez-Selem, 2005).
49 Glacial landforms asso-ciated with the Last Glacial Maximum (LGM; ~26.5–
50 19 ka; Clark et al., 2009) persist in the tropics of America such as Mexico,
51 Guatemala, Costa Rica and the Andes (Mark et al., 2005; Vázquez-Selem and
52 Lachniet, 2017) because glaciers shaped effectively the landscapes (Porter,
53 2001; Lachniet and Vázquez-Selem, 2005). One important parameter on glacial
54 reconstruction is the Equilibrium Line Altitude (ELA), an imaginary line where
55 the net balance at the end of the ab-lation season equals to 0 (Paterson, 1994;
56 Benn et al., 2005). This al-titude is rarely constant throughout a glacier, being
57 sensitive to changes in several factors, e.g. snow accumulation and shading
58 (Benn et al., 2005).

59 Despite the studies realized in the region, an updated and detailed estimation of
60 the ELAs during the LGM has not been carried out so far such as Chirripó
61 National Park (Costa Rica). Furthermore, previous paleo-ELA estimations
62 (Orvis and Horn, 2000; Lachniet and Seltzer, 2002) covered only small
63 extensions of the Chirripó National park on Valle Talari and Valle de las

64 Morrenas with less detail scales ($\geq 1: 50,000$). Orvis and Horn (2000) used larger
65 and older moraines and associated trimlines to reconstruct the ELAs of three
66 paleoglaciers in the Valle de las Morrenas near the Cerro Chirripó massif. The
67 results suggest a paleo-ELA between 3500 and 3550 m a.s.l. and an average
68 temperature between 6 and 8 °C colder during the LGM than as today (Islebe
69 and Hooghiemstra, 1997). These moraine sequences have been recently dated
70 using ^{10}Be and ^{36}Cl cosmic ray exposure (CRE), con-firming a maximum
71 expansion 21–18 ka BP ago in agreement with the global LGM (Cunningham
72 et al., 2019; Potter et al., 2019).

73 Other studies carried out in the circum-Caribbean region used sev-eral methods
74 to reconstruct the paleo-ELAs, ELA depression and pa-leotemperatures. These
75 LGM paleo-ELA studies are assumed to be si-milar in terms of time. Lachniet
76 and Seltzer (2002) estimated a paleo-ELA between 3532 and 3502 m a.s.l. in
77 Cordillera de Tamanca through AAR and THAR methods using ratios of 0.70
78 whereas Lachniet and Vázquez-Selem (2005) reported a paleo-ELA between
79 3528–3508 m a.s.l. (AABR = 1.8) and 3489–3464 m a.s.l. (AABR = 4.0).
80 Similar values (3470 and 3670 m a.s.l.) were obtained in Altos de
81 Cuchumatanes (Guatemala) with higher AABR ratios (2.0–5.0) (Roy and
82 Lachniet, 2010). However, Vázquez-Selem (2000) suggested higher values
83 (3650–4090 m a.s.l.; THAR 0.2 and 0.5) in Iztaccíhuatl volcano (Central
84 Mexico) than Cofre de Perote and Tancítaro (Mexico) (3650 m a.s.l. and 3390
85 m a.s.l., respectively; THAR 0.4). To the south, paleo-ELA was calculated
86 between 4228 m a.s.l (AABR = 1.8), and 4104 m a.s.l. (AABR = 4.0) in Sierra
87 Nevada de Santa Marta (Co-lombia) and 4070 m a.s.l. (THAR 0.4) in Sierra
88 Nevada de Cocuy (Co-lombia) whereas Bogota area (Colombia) and Cordillera
89 Central (Co-lombia) reached higher altitudes (3345 with THAR 0.4 and 3480
90 m a.s.l. with THAR 0.2, respectively; Lachniet and Vázquez-Selem, 2005).
91 Moreover, an interval between 3210 and 4030 m a.s.l (AAR 0.66–0.87 and
92 AABR = 5, 10, 15) has been defined in the Cordillera de Merida (Venezuela)
93 (Stansell et al., 2007).

94 Paleo-ELA depression reconstructions fluctuate between ~1300–1500 m in
95 Costa Rica, Guatemala, the mexican volcanoes Tancítaro and Cofre de Perote,
96 in Bogotá area (Colombia) and Cordillera Central (Colombia) but values less

97 pronounced (~500–1000 m) have been established in Iztaccíhuatl (Mexico),
98 Sierra Nevada de Santa Marta (Colombia) and Sierra Nevada de Cocuy
99 (Colombia) (Lachniet and Vázquez-Selem, 2005). An intermediate in-terval
100 (850–1420 m) has been estimated in the Cordillera de Merida (Venezuela). On
101 the other hand, paleotemperature reconstructions based on ELA depression
102 reveal severe cold conditions during the LGM in the circum-Caribbean region.
103 Roy and Lachniet (2010) proposed a temperature decrease between 5.9 and 7.6
104 °C in Sierra de Cuchuma-tanes (Guatemala) whereas Stansell et al. (2007) and
105 Vázquez-Selem and Lachniet (2017) suggested a greater cooling (6–9 °C) in the
106 Mexican volcanoes and Cordillera de Merida (Venezuela).

107 In this study, we improve the paleo-ELA calculations and review the
108 paleotemperature estimations in Chirripó National Park in Costa Rica. Based
109 on previous studies, the average ELA during the LGM should be located at
110 3500–3600 m a.s.l., experiencing a depression of ~1300–1500 m due to a
111 significant cooling (6–8 °C). We evaluate this hypothesis by reconstructing the
112 glaciers of Chirripó National Park during the LGM period. Moreover, we
113 estimated the paleo-ELAs through a Geographical Information System (GIS)
114 tool that allows their automatic calculation (Pellitero et al., 2015). The
115 paleotemperatures decrease was estimated by multiplying several modern lapse
116 rates by the ELA depression (Kuhn, 1989; Stansell et al., 2007). In addition, we
117 analyzed different microscale topo-climatic variables that explain the
118 determined paleo-ELAs areas (Boehner and Antonic, 2009).

119

120 2. Regional setting

121

122 The study area is in the Cordillera de Talamanca, the most promi-nent mountain
123 system in Central America, extending 175 km from the central-southern portion
124 of Costa Rica to the eastern sector of Panama (Marshall, 2007). The Chirripó
125 National Park is in the central and southern parts of the Cordillera de Talamanca.
126 Cerro Chirripó contains the highest peak of Costa Rica with 3820 m a.s.l. (Fig.
127 1).

128 The landscape of the Chirripó National Park is the result of complex tectonics.
129 Its architecture has a direct relation to the subduction processes between the
130 Cocos and Caribbean plates with implications on regional volcanism and
131 seismicity (DeMets et al., 2010). In SE Costa Rica, the collision of the Cocos
132 Ridge, a sequence of an oceanic crust growth from the Galapagos hotspot,
133 stopped volcanism in the Cordillera de Talamanca about 2 Ma ago (Morell et
134 al., 2012). Geology includes plutonic rocks, granodiorites and volcanic rocks
135 that have been exposed between 12 and 7.8 Ma as well as andesites and basalts
136 ranging in age from 29 to 7 Ma (Denyer and Alvarado, 2007; Alfaro et al.,
137 2018). Geomorphology of this territory is defined by a high uplift rates ranging
138 from 1.7 to 8.5 m kyr⁻¹ (Gardner et al., 2013; Quesada Román and Zamorano
139 Orozco, 2019b), under the control of faulting with NW-SE and N-S orientations
140 (Alvarado et al., 2009; Camacho et al., 2020). Volcanic slopes shaped by glacial
141 or periglacial action characterize the glacial landscape (Quesada-Román and
142 Zamorano-Orozco, 2019). The results are well-preserved cirques, arêtes,
143 moraines, till deposits and glacial lakes above 3000 m a.s.l. (Quesada-Román
144 et al., 2019). Today, there are no glaciers in the summits of Chirripó National
145 Park.

146 Climatic conditions are dominated by northeast trade winds, the latitudinal
147 migration of the Intertropical Convergence Zone (ITCZ), cold fronts, and
148 tropical cyclones (Alfaro et al., 2010; Campos-Durán and Quesada-Román,
149 2017; Maldonado et al., 2018). These circulation processes produce two rainfall
150 maxima, one in May and another one in October, which are interrupted by a
151 relative minimum between July and August known as the Mid-Summer Drought
152 (Maldonado et al., 2016; Quesada-Román and Zamorano-Orozco, 2018).
153 Historical records show that ~89% of the precipitation falls among May and
154 November (wet season). As a result, a well-defined dry season is established
155 from December to April with average temperatures in the study area of 9.7 °C
156 (Fig. 2; Quesada-Román, 2017). Local LGM intensification lapse rate may be
157 related to the combination of an equatorward restriction of the ITCZ and more
158 frequent incursions of polar-air masses (Lachniet and Seltzer, 2002).

159 Different types of mountainous forests and peatlands compose the vegetation of
160 the Cordillera de Talamanca. At elevations exceeding 3000 m, highland páramo

161 landscapes prevail, a grassy or shrub-dominated ecosystem typical of cool and
162 wet upper hills of tropical mountains (Kappelle and Horn, 2016). Along the
163 Costa Rican páramo, hundreds of palustrine and lacustrine wetlands have an
164 important hydrological and ecological regional function (Esquivel-Hernández
165 et al., 2018, Veas-Ayala et al., 2018).

166

167 3. Materials and methods

168

169 3.1. Paleo-equilibrium line altitude reconstruction

170

171 The ELA values for the glaciers during the LGM were obtained from the
172 contour lines and the glacier delimitation. First, from contour lines (10 m
173 contour interval) of the study area provided by CARTA - Costa Rica Airborne
174 Research and Technology Applications (2005). LGM contour lines were created
175 based on the previous studies in the area (Lachniet and Seltzer, 2002; Lachniet
176 and Vázquez-Selem, 2005). After that, and based on the observed glacier
177 dynamics, we reduced the ice thickness in areas where there is significant “draw
178 down” from outlet glaciers or where the ice surface is steep (Paterson, 1994;
179 Rea et al., 1998; Cowton et al., 2009; Campos et al., 2019). Then, a Digital Ele-
180 vation Model (DEM) was performed using the software ESRI ArcGIS

181 10.1 and the LGM contour lines were transformed into a triangulated irregular
182 network (TIN) and later transformed into a raster in order to obtain the DEM.
183 The paleoglaciers were delimited by digitizing the limits proposed by Lachniet
184 and Seltzer (2002), which realized several field surveys in most of the glaciated
185 valleys of the study area. Additionally, several field surveys have been carried
186 out in the years 2016, 2017 and 2018 with the aim of reviewing some
187 geomorphological features that may confirm the extent of the glaciers during
188 the LGM (Quesada-Román et al., 2019).

189 Once the digitizing of the paleoglaciers was finished, a DEM of each
190 paleoglacier was obtained separately, in order to calculate their paleo-ELAs.
191 There are several methods to determine the value of the ELA: the Median

192 Glacier Elevation (MGE), the Area Altitude (AA), the Accumulation Area Ratio
193 (AAR) and the Area Altitude Balance Ratio (AABR). Kurowski's (1891)
194 introduced the MGE method, which pro-poses that the ELA is located at the
195 average altitude of the glacier, as-suming that the glacier is in equilibrium where
196 the mass balance has a linear relationship with the altitude from the glacier front
197 to the header. The AA method assumes that the ratio of the accumulation and
198 ablation gradients is constant, and its value is equal to 1. The AAR method as-
199 sumes that the ratio between the accumulation and the ablation areas is constant
200 if glaciers are in steady state but does not consider the mass balance gradient
201 (Pellitero et al., 2015). Finally, the AABR method contemplates the glacier
202 hypsometry and assumes that the mass bal-ance gradient consists of
203 approximately two linear segments, normally with different slopes above and
204 below the ELA, and uses a balance ratio for the estimation (Osmaston's, 2005).
205 The paleo-ELAs were obtained by using a GIS tool coded with Python for ESRI
206 ArcGIS developed by Pellitero et al. (2015) and the values were calculated
207 using the MGE, the AA, the AAR and the AABR methods. This tool follows the
208 Kurowski (1891) methodology for the MGE method, the Serrano and González-
209 Trueba (2004) approach for the AAR and the Osmaston (2005) proce-dure for
210 the AABR and AA, being the AA method equivalent to an AABR with a BR =
211 1.

212 The ELAs calculated with the AAR and AABR methods were de-termined for
213 several ratios. These methods were those that offer the most accurate results for
214 the study of the paleo-ELAs, being the re-presentative ratios 0.65 for the AAR
215 method and 2.0 for the AABR method. For the AAR method the ratios applied
216 range from 0.5 to 0.75, although Benn and Evans (1998) pointed out that the
217 AAR in steady-state glaciers at mid and high latitudes range from 0.5 to 0.8.
218 Kaser and Osmaston (2002) consider the AAR 0.67 to be the most appropriate
219 for tropical glaciers. The most frequently used ratio for the AAR calculation is
220 0.6 ± 0.05 (Porter, 2001). This ratio is generally considered to characterize
221 steady-state conditions for valley/cirque glaciers (Meier and Post, 1962;
222 Andrews, 1975; Porter, 1975; Gross et al., 1977; Meierding, 1982; Sutherland,
223 1984; Hawkins, 1985; Ballantyne, 1989; Leonard, 1989; Locke, 1989; Nesje,
224 1992; Campos et al., 2019). For the AABR calculations method, the applied BR
225 ranged from 1 to 3. Rea (2009) proposed as “representative” a global AABR of

226 1.75 ± 0.71. AABRs between 1.8 and 2.2 were proposed for mid-latitude
227 maritime glaciers (Benn and Gemmell, 1997; Benn and Evans, 1998; Benn and
228 Lehmkuhl, 2000). Finally, high AABRs are assumed for tropical glaciers
229 because there are high ablation rates throughout the year. For this method, we
230 used the ratio 2.0 as the most accurate because we assumed that tropical
231 glaciers had high ablation ratios and, according to Rea (2009), tropical glaciers
232 tend to have small ablation areas. Determined paleo-glaciers were named
233 according to the official topographical maps, summits or rivers names.

234

235 3.2. Paleotemperature reconstruction

236

237 The paleotemperature reconstruction during the LGM is based on the estimation
238 of the ELA depression (Δ ELA). To calculate the Δ ELA, we used the modern
239 ELA (5100 m a. s. l. in 1958 AD; Lachniet and Vázquez-Selem (2005) from
240 Sierra Nevada de Santa Marta (Colombia) because Cerro Chirripó is ice-free
241 today and both areas have similar climate conditions (Rabatel et al., 2018;
242 Méndez et al., 2019). Sierra de Santa Marta is located at 10.5° N at ~1100 km
243 east to Chirripó National Park (9.29° N). We calculated the paleotemperatures
244 applying three lapse rates: 0.55 °C/100 m; 0.65 °C/100 m and 0.75 °C/100 m.
245 The first (0.55 °C/100 m) and the last values (0.75 °C/100 m) are considered
246 plausible minimum and maximum lapse rates in the tropical atmosphere during
247 the LGM (Stansell et al., 2007). Therefore, we chose 0.65 °C/100 m as our
248 reference lapse rate (Table S1).

249

250 3.3. Land surface parameters analysis

251

252 First, we calculated and extracted the mean value of each paleo-ELAs polygon
253 of seven land surface parameters (LSP). We considered Basin location (B),
254 Analytical Hillshading (AH; Tarini et al., 2006), Aspect (ASP), Area Surface
255 Radiation (ASR; Boehner and Antonic, 2009), Diurnal Anisotropic Heating
256 (DAH; Boehner and Antonic, 2009), Slope (SLO), Terrain Ruggedness Index

257 (TRI; Riley et al., 1999), and Wind Exposition (WE; Boehner and Antonic,
258 2009) using SAGA soft-ware (Conrad et al., 2015). Second, we apply a Pearson
259 correlation method (Vinod, 2017), and performed a generalized linear model
260 (GLM) to describe linkages between obtained paleo-ELAs areas (A) and LSP.
261 Based on Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) (Anderson and Burnham, 2004),
262 we used a backward selection to contrast the full hypothesis (i.e. $\tilde{A} B + AH +$
263 $ASP + ASR + DAH + SLO + TRI + WE$) against the alternative hypothesis (i.e.
264 $\tilde{A} AH + TRI + WE$). All co-variables were first standardized using z-score.
265 Finally, model para-meters were used to evaluate the weight of each co-variable
266 interaction explaining the paleo-glacier areas.

267

268 4. Results

269

270 4.1. Paleo-ELA for Chirripó National Park

271

272 The ELA values for the paleoglaciers of the study area during the LGM were
273 calculated using the MGE, AA, AAR and AABR methods using several ratios.
274 The results are presented in Table 1. Using the AAR method (with ratio 0.65),
275 the mean paleo-ELA was located at 3492 m a.s.l. whereas the individual paleo-
276 ELA values for the glaciers of the study area ranges from 3247 m a.s.l. in the
277 Cerro Urán 3 glacier to 3679 m a. s. l. in the glacier Cerro Ventisqueros 1. The
278 AABR method (with ratio 2.0) provides paleo-ELA values similar to AAR
279 (0.65), being the mean paleo-ELA the same as calculated with the AAR method,
280 3492 m a.s.l. The lower and higher paleo-ELA values were found also on glacier
281 Cerro Urán 3 (3251 m a.s.l.), and Cerro Ventisqueros 1 (3679 m a.s.l.). The
282 differences between these glaciers are due to glacier Cerro Ventisqueros 1 was
283 smaller than the glacier Cerro Urán 3 (0.08 km² vs 0.30 km²: Table 2).
284 Furthermore, the glacier Cerro Urán 3 was located at lower altitude (mean
285 altitudes of 3302 m vs 3640 m). The obtained ELA values for the rest of the
286 glaciers were similar using both AAR (ratio 0.65) and AABR (ratio 2.0)
287 methods. Regarding the distribution of the ice, the biggest glaciers (Valle Talari,

288 Pico Noreste, Lagos Chir-ripó, Cerro Pirámide, Río Chirripó and Valle Las
289 Morrenas), had the main part of the ice of the study area during the LGM with
290 58.3% of the total glaciated area (Table 2). There is a difference of ~85 m in the
291 mean ELA values between glaciers from Pacific (higher) and Caribbean basins
292 (using the AAR method).

293

294 4.2. Regional and local climatic reconstruction

295

296 If the modern ELA in Sierra Nevada de Santa Marta (Colombia) was located at
297 5100 m a. s. l. in 1958 AD, the Δ ELA was ~1600 m during the LGM in Cerro
298 Chirripó. This Δ ELA represents an average temperature decrease of ~10.5 °C
299 both AAR (0.65) and AABR (2.0) methods when a lapse rate of 0.65 °C/100 m
300 is used. Average temperature decrease obtained with lower (0.55 °C/100 m) and
301 higher (0.75 °C/100 m) lapse rates are ~ 9 °C and ~12 °C, respectively (Table
302 S1).

303

304 4.3. Paleo-glacier areas analysis

305

306 Statistical analyses of the determined paleo-ELAs areas with land surface
307 parameters (LSP) based on the AIC criterion supports the alternative model
308 (AIC_{Ha} = 89.18) against the full hypothesis (AIC_{Hf} = 104.77). In addition, the
309 model suggests that the best generalized linear model supports an interaction
310 between Analytical Hillshading (AH), Terrain Ruggedness Index (TRI) and
311 Wind Exposition (WE; $AREA \sim AH + TRI + WE$). Table 3 provides the model
312 parameters, also indicating that the most significant influence on onset
313 probability of paleo-glacier areas are given by WE and TRI, as shown by z-ratio
314 tests of parameter estimates.

315 Caribbean Basin glaciers sum 58% out of the total and 60% of the entire glacial
316 area (Table 2). The most influential LSP according the GLM that show
317 interesting associations (Fig. 3) were TRI and WE. Both smaller and larger

318 Pacific glaciers tended to develop better in Terrain Ruggedness Index values
319 around 30. Meanwhile, Caribbean glaciers have higher TRI values (~ 40) in little
320 units but interestingly similar values than Pacific glaciers in the larger units.
321 Low TRI value explains larger paleo-glacier areas such as Valle Talari, Lagos
322 Chirripó, and Valle Las Morrenas (Fig. 4). In addition, TRI and SLOPE had a
323 large positive correlation, which explain why slopes between 20 and 30°
324 comprise bigger area units. Wind Exposition demonstrated a clearer relationship
325 with both smaller and larger glaciers in the Pacific Basin, possibly due to its
326 position in the leeward side of Cordillera de Talamanca.

327

328 5. Discussion

329

330 In this study, we perform a complete ELA reconstruction in Chirripó
331 paleoglacier system through MGE, AA, AAR and AABR methods during the
332 LGM. We will focus the discussion in the AAR and AABR because they are
333 considered the most appropriate methods for ELA re-constructions (Osmaston,
334 2005; Rea, 2009; Benn and Hulton, 2010; Campos et al., 2019). Regarding the
335 AAR method, we chose the paleo-ELA values derived of the ratio 0.65 because
336 this value has been frequently used in tropical regions (Porter, 2001; Osmaston,
337 2005) whereas a balance ratio of 2.0 is typical for the AABR in the extra-tropical
338 glaciers (Lachniet and Vázquez-Selem, 2005). The results show that the
339 methods AAR (0.65) and AABR (2.0) are in close correspondence in Chirripó
340 National Park, with an average paleo-ELA of ~ 3490 m a.s.l. This value is also
341 similar to previous paleo-ELAs re-constructions in Costa Rica and Guatemala
342 using several ratios and methods (Lachniet and Seltzer, 2002; Lachniet and
343 Vázquez-Selem, 2005; Roy and Lachniet, 2010). However, Iztaccíhuatl volcano
344 (Central Mexico) show higher paleo-ELAs (~ 150 – 600 m), based on THAR
345 (0.2–0.5) method (Vázquez-Selem, 2000). This difference could be due to
346 precipitation decreased associated with continental conditions of Iztaccíhuatl
347 despite the active monsoon produced by the proximal location of the
348 Intertropical Convergence Zone (ITCZ) to the Mexican landmass during the
349 LGM (Lachniet et al., 2013). Cofre de Perote and Tancítaro (Mexico), located

350 ~100 km from the Gulf of Mexico and ~150 km from the Pacific coast
351 respectively, confirm the oceanic influence as the paleo-ELA was situated at
352 3650 m a.s.l. and 3390 m a.s.l. (THAR 0.4), a similar altitude than Chirripó. By
353 contrast, the re-construction in the northern Andes exhibits heterogeneous
354 paleo-ELAs.

355 In Colombia, the paleo-ELA was ~700 m (AABR 1.8) and ~600 m (AABR 4.0;
356 THAR 0.4) higher in Sierra Nevada de Santa Marta and Sierra Nevada de Cocuy
357 than Chirripó although in the Bogotá area was

358 ~150 m (THAR 0.4) lower (Lachniet and Vázquez-Selem, 2005). However, a
359 similar value (THAR 0.2) than Chirripó was obtained in Cordillera Central
360 (Colombia) (Lachniet and Vázquez-Selem, 2005). In addition, Stansell et al.
361 (2007) used higher AABR ratios (BR = 5, 10, 15) in several areas of the
362 Cordillera de Merida (Venezuela) obtaining similar values to Chirripó except in
363 Paramo de Piedras Blancas where the average paleo-ELA was ~400 m higher.
364 When all these results are globally compared, there are not significant
365 differences between methods (AABR, AAR and THAR) and procedures
366 (manual and auto-mated) except some areas where local factors (e.g. continental
367 climate, aspect, and shading) can likely produce higher or lower paleo-ELAs.
368 Moreover, it must be noticed that paleo-ELAs derived from higher ratios (BR =
369 5, 10, 15) are mostly in agreement with lower ratios (BR = 1.8, 2.0) in the AABR
370 method. This implies that it is not necessary the use of BR ratios higher than 5
371 for paleo-ELA reconstructions at least in the circum-Caribbean region. Our
372 study, using an automated approach, also confirms the previous estimations
373 provided by Orvis and Horn (2000) in Chirripó National Park and the
374 reconstructions performed in Costa Rica and Guatemala by Lachniet and Seltzer
375 (2002), Lachniet and Vázquez-Selem (2005), and Roy and Lachniet (2010).

376 As paleo-ELA values derived from AAR (0.65) and AABR (BR = 2.0) methods
377 are statistically identical in Chirripó National Park, there are no differences
378 between their ELA depression and paleotemperature estimates. Thus, the ELA
379 depression was ~1600 m, and the temperature was ~10 °C lower than modern
380 values assuming the modern ELA from Sierra Nevada de Santa Marta (5100 m
381 a.s.l. in 1958 AD). This data coincides with the values suggested by Lachniet
382 and Vázquez-Selem (2005) in Costa Rica, Altos de Cuchumatanes (Guatemala),

383 and Tancí-taro volcano (Mexico) but the estimations are higher in Iztaccíhuatl
384 (~600 m) (Central Mexico) and Cofre de Perote (300–400 m) (Mexico)
385 (Vázquez-Selem, 2000; Lachniet and Vázquez-Selem, 2005). Roy and Lachniet
386 (2010) have also reported a higher value similar to Iztaccí-huatl and Cofre de
387 Perote in Sierra los Cuchumatanes (~200–500 m). A higher estimation in
388 Iztaccíhuatl could be due to the continental climate whereas the value of Cofre
389 de Perote is not realistic because Lachniet and Vázquez-Selem (2005) used the
390 modern ELA from Iztaccíhuatl (continental conditions). Furthermore, the
391 reconstruction carried out by Roy and Lachniet (2010) is based on the use of
392 the modern 0 °C isotherm as modern reference ELA to calculate the ELA
393 depression. According to Stansell et al. (2007), the modern 0 °C isotherm is
394 difficult to determine, and it not always coincide with the ELA of the existing
395 glacier (Stansell et al., 2007). The ELA depression also reached higher values
396 (~200–800 m) in Sierra de Santa Marta (Colombia), Sierra Nevada de Cocuy
397 (Colombia), and Cordillera de Merida (Venezuela) (Lachniet and Vázquez-
398 Selem, 2005; Stansell et al., 2007) than Chirripó but the data are similar
399 compared to Bogotá area and Cordillera Central (Colombia) (Lachniet and
400 Vázquez-Selem, 2005). These heterogeneous values could be due to local
401 factors such as precipitation changes, cloud cover, wind direction, and aspect.
402 Another reason that usually produces differences in the ELA depression
403 reconstruction is the absence of a well-defined age of the moraine record or the
404 use of a non-reference method for the modern ELA estimation. For example,
405 Vázquez-Selem (2000) applied the THAR (0.4) on Iztaccíhuatl whereas
406 Stansell et al. (2007) used an equation that includes the estimated annual
407 freezing height and the annual precipitation. All these reasons and the appli-
408 cation of several atmospheric lapse rates determine the observed differences in
409 paleotemperatures estimations. Our estimation of ~10 °C in Chirripó National
410 Park is notably colder than the reconstructions in Sierra los Cuchumatanes (5.9–
411 7.6 °C; Guatemala; Roy and Lachniet, 2010) although it is almost in agreement
412 with Mexican volcanoes (9–6 °C; Vázquez-Selem and Heine, 2011) and
413 Cordillera de Merida (8.8 °C; Venezuela; Stansell et al., 2007). Other
414 paleoclimate records such as Mexican speleothem reconstruction and magnetic
415 susceptibility measurements in Lake Petén Itzá (Guatemala) suggest a
416 Mesoamerican monsoon strengthening driven by a proximal ITCZ to Mexico

417 during the LGM, implying wet conditions in the Atlantic and Pacific coasts of
418 Central America (Hodell et al., 2008; Lachniet et al., 2009, 2013; Escobar et al.,
419 2012). Therefore, wet and cold conditions prevailed in the continent of the
420 circum-Caribbean region during the LGM.

421 Local land surface parameters showed interesting controls that probably
422 governed the paleo-glacier extension and distribution. Diurnal Anisotropic
423 Heating (DAH) and Area Surface Radiation (ASR) did not show a significant
424 relationship with the area of the paleo-glaciers ($-0.38 - 0.32$) and ($2.1-2.45$).
425 This is probably explained by the low insolation fluctuations that occur on low
426 latitudes (Liou, 2002; Gablar et al., 2009). Generally, climate in the Chirripó
427 National Park is controlled by north-east trade winds, the Intertropical
428 Convergence Zone migration, cold fronts, and tropical cyclones (Esquivel-
429 Hernández et al., 2019). Wind Exposition (WE) and Terrain Ruggedness Index
430 (TRI) showed a significant statistical relationship with the paleo-ELAs gla-ciers
431 areas. Wind characteristics such as direction, velocity, seasonality and
432 temperature can affect the processes that govern accumulation or ablation of
433 glacial, meaning that there is a relationship between local wind fields and the
434 behavior and snow accumulation of glacierized areas (Dadic et al., 2010).
435 Accurate modeling of wind dynamics over complex landscapes such as Chirripó
436 National Park can give new in-sights for understanding glacial development.
437 Local wind dynamics probably affected differently the distribution of heat
438 budgets thru air temperature variability causing glacier fragmentation and
439 impacts on mass balance during the LGM (Carturan et al., 2015).

440 TRI resulted in a negative correlation (~ 20) with the area of the paleo-glaciers,
441 larger areas tend to have lower TRI values. Bed rough-ness exerts a major
442 control on an ice mass's basal motion (Li et al., 2010). Caribbean basin higher
443 TRI values of TRI can be explained by the action of continuous orographic
444 precipitation over the windward generating more erosion. On the other hand,
445 the Pacific Basin has larger areas of paleo-glaciers and lower values of TRI.
446 Rock surface weath-ering often leads to increased rock surface roughness
447 (McCarrol and Nesje, 1996). This is consistent with the Caribbean basin higher
448 rates of basal sliding and rock glacial dynamics of the paleo-glaciers may be
449 linked with the roughness index. We suppose that higher velocities and melting

450 of the paleoglacials caused increased rates of glacial abrasion on Caribbean
451 basin.

452

453 6. Conclusions

454

455 We performed a complete ELA reconstruction in Chirripó paleoglacier system
456 during the LGM. We obtained an average paleo-ELA of ~3490 m a.s.l. using
457 the methods AAR (ratio 0.65) and AABR (ratio 2.0). Assuming a modern ELA
458 of ~5100 m a.s.l. (Sierra Nevada de Santa Marta, Colombia), we estimated an
459 ELA depression of ~1600 m and a temperature decrease of ~10 °C compared to
460 modern values. Wind Exposition (WE) and Terrain Ruggedness Index (TRI)
461 were the land surface parameters with a significant statistical relationship with
462 the paleo-glacier areas. In general, these values are analogous to other mountain
463 areas of the circum-Caribbean region, suggesting cold conditions in the region
464 during the LGM if we assume that ELA is mainly modulated by temperature.

465

466 Author agreement statement

467

468 We the undersigned declare that this manuscript is original, has not been
469 published before and is not currently being considered for publication
470 elsewhere. We confirm that the manuscript has been read and approved by all
471 named authors and that there are no other persons who satisfied the criteria for
472 authorship but are not listed. We further confirm that the order of authors listed
473 in the manuscript has been approved by all of us. We understand that the
474 Corresponding Author is the sole contact for the Editorial process. He is
475 responsible for communicating with the other authors about progress,
476 submissions of revisions and final approval of proofs.

477

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674 Fig. 1. Regional location of Chirripó National Park, ITCZ position during
 675 winter (January) and summer (July), and numbered paleoglaciérs: 1, Cerro
 676 Amó; 2, Los Arrepentidos; 3, Cerro Terbi 1; 4, Cerro Terbi 2; 5, Pico Sureste;
 677 6, Bosin; 7, Cerro Ventisqueros 1; 8, Cerro Ventisqueros 2; 9, Cerro
 678 Ventisqueros 3; 10, Valle Talari; 11, Pico Noreste; 12, Lagos Chirripó; 13, Cerro
 679 Pirámide; 14, Cerro Truncado; 15, Cerro Urán 1; 16, Cerro Urán 2; 17, Cerro
 680 Urán 3; 18, Cerro Urán 4; 19, Río Chirripó Pacífico 1; 20, Río Chirripó Pacífico
 681 2; 21, Río Chirripó; 22, Valle Las Morrenas; 23, Cerro Laguna; 24, Chirripó
 682 Grande 1; 25, Chirripó Grande 2; 26, Chirripó Grande 3; 27, Fila Norte 1; 28,
 683 Fila Norte 2; 29, Fila Norte 3; 30, Fila Norte 4; 31, Fila Norte 5.

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685

686 Fig. 2. Mean temperature (°C) and precipitation (mm) of Chirripó
 687 Meteorological Station (3630 m a.s.l.) between 1995 and 2009 (IMN – Instituto
 688 Meteorológico Nacional, 2009).

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691 Fig. 3. Relationship between paleo-glacier areas, Terrain Ruggedness Index (a)
 692 and Wind Exposition (b), according Caribbean (red) and Pacific (green) basins.
 693 (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is
 694 referred to the Web version of this article.)

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696

697 Fig. 4. Overview of Valle Talari (a), Lagos Chirripó (b), Valle Las Morrenas (c),
698 the biggest paleoglaciers of Chirripó National Park.

699

700

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701 Table 1

702 Results of ELA calculation, using different methods and ratios. Median Glacier
703 Elevation (MGE), Area Altitude (AA), Accumulation Area Ratio (AAR), Area
704 Altitude Balance Ratio (AABR).

GLACIER	MGE	AA	AAR										
			0.5	0.55	0.6	0.65	0.7	0.75	1.0	1.5	2.0	2.5	3.0
Cerro Amó	3399	3391	3399	3398	3397	3395	3393	3391	3393	3391	3389	3387	3386
Los Arrepentidos	3331	3346	3331	3313	3305	3299	3293	3285	3347	3334	3326	3319	3314
Cerro Terbi 1	3609	3598	3609	3599	3590	3581	3571	3555	3600	3588	3580	3574	3568
Cerro Terbi 2	3518	3518	3518	3506	3496	3487	3478	3471	3519	3509	3502	3497	3493
Pico Sureste	3516	3507	3516	3513	3510	3506	3500	3494	3509	3503	3499	3496	3493
Bosin	3655	3653	3655	3654	3653	3652	3650	3649	3655	3653	3652	3651	3651
Cerro Ventisqueros 1	3683	3680	3683	3681	3680	3679	3677	3676	3681	3680	3679	3678	3677
Cerro Ventisqueros 2	3430	3428	3430	3420	3409	3399	3389	3378	3429	3418	3411	3405	3400
Cerro Ventisqueros 3	3591	3588	3591	3588	3585	3582	3578	3575	3589	3586	3583	3581	3579
Valle Talari	3605	3584	3605	3594	3584	3576	3570	3561	3586	3571	3560	3550	3542
Pico Noreste	3502	3498	3502	3492	3483	3473	3462	3450	3500	3487	3478	3471	3466
Lagos Chirripó	3668	3618	3668	3654	3635	3615	3594	3574	3620	3603	3590	3580	3571
Cerro Pirámide	3561	3554	3561	3545	3529	3517	3506	3495	3556	3541	3530	3522	3516
Cerro Truncado	3568	3559	3568	3559	3549	3538	3528	3516	3561	3550	3542	3535	3530
Cerro Urán 1	3390	3387	3390	3385	3380	3376	3371	3367	3388	3384	3380	3378	3376
Cerro Urán 2	3452	3431	3452	3449	3442	3431	3421	3409	3432	3425	3419	3415	3411
Cerro Urán 3	3288	3273	3288	3277	3266	3247	3217	3205	3274	3261	3251	3244	3238
Cerro Urán 4	3433	3425	3433	3421	3410	3398	3387	3375	3427	3416	3408	3402	3398
Río Chirripó Pacífico 1	3671	3668	3671	3668	3666	3663	3661	3658	3669	3667	3665	3664	3663
Río Chirripó Pacífico 2	3639	3637	3639	3636	3633	3630	3627	3624	3639	3636	3633	3632	3630
Río Chirripó	3590	3573	3590	3577	3565	3549	3529	3508	3574	3557	3545	3536	3528
Valle Las Morrenas	3594	3568	3594	3585	3573	3562	3547	3528	3570	3553	3539	3529	3519
Cerro Laguna	3574	3553	3574	3563	3550	3537	3524	3511	3554	3543	3535	3529	3524
Chirripó Grande 1	3522	3520	3522	3520	3518	3516	3514	3512	3521	3519	3517	3516	3515
Chirripó Grande 2	3557	3533	3557	3544	3531	3518	3507	3495	3535	3523	3515	3508	3502
Chirripó Grande 3	3407	3404	3407	3401	3395	3389	3383	3377	3405	3398	3394	3390	3387
Fila Norte 1	3485	3456	3485	3480	3474	3460	3434	3418	3458	3448	3440	3435	3430
Fila Norte 2	3502	3500	3502	3500	3499	3497	3496	3495	3502	3500	3499	3498	3497
Fila Norte 3	3388	3386	3388	3382	3376	3371	3364	3358	3388	3381	3377	3374	3371
Fila Norte 4	3470	3454	3470	3463	3454	3445	3433	3421	3455	3446	3439	3434	3429
Fila Norte 5	3398	3396	3398	3395	3393	3390	3387	3385	3397	3394	3393	3391	3390

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707 Table 2

708 Morphometric data of the studied paleoglaciers. Equilibrium Line Altitude
709 Accumulation Area Ratio (ELA AAR), Equilibrium Line Altitude Area Altitude
710 Balance Ratio (ELA AABR).

Glacier	Basin	Altitude (m)		Length (m)	Area (km ²)	ELA AAR	ELA AABR
		Max	Min			(0.65)	(2.0)
Cerro Amó	Pacific	3410	3295	2340	1.49	3395	3389
Los Arrepentidos	Pacific	3524	3195	985	0.41	3299	3326
Cerro Terbi 1	Pacific	3700	3397	1238	0.40	3581	3580
Cerro Terbi 2	Pacific	3610	3393	1710	0.76	3487	3502
Pico Sureste	Pacific	3573	3360	945	0.42	3506	3499
Bosin	Pacific	3680	3579	580	0.13	3652	3652
Cerro Ventisqueros 1	Pacific	3696	3585	404	0.08	3679	3679
Cerro Ventisqueros 2	Pacific	3556	3293	300	0.05	3399	3411
Cerro Ventisqueros 3	Pacific	3683	3535	680	0.13	3582	3583
Valle Talari	Pacific	3700	3198	4050	4.33	3576	3560
Pico Noreste	Caribbean	3661	3265	1970	1.45	3473	3478
Lagos Chirripó	Pacific	3740	3162	2850	2.89	3615	3590
Cerro Pirámide	Caribbean	3705	3148	2695	1.78	3517	3530
Cerro Truncado	Caribbean	3689	3365	1302	0.63	3538	3542
Cerro Urán 1	Caribbean	3495	3231	584	0.14	3376	3380
Cerro Urán 2	Caribbean	3495	3222	1225	0.36	3431	3419
Cerro Urán 3	Caribbean	3469	3134	1005	0.30	3247	3251
Cerro Urán 4	Caribbean	3532	3306	1165	0.30	3398	3408
Río Chirripó Pacífico 1	Pacific	3696	3603	355	0.05	3663	3665
Río Chirripó Pacífico 2	Pacific	3698	3584	790	0.21	3630	3633
Río Chirripó	Caribbean	3700	3240	2808	1.94	3549	3545
Valle Las Morrenas	Caribbean	3700	3132	4255	4.08	3562	3539
Cerro Laguna	Caribbean	3653	3370	1450	1.10	3537	3535
Chirripó Grande 1	Caribbean	3597	3491	630	0.14	3516	3517
Chirripó Grande 2	Caribbean	3650	3251	2545	1.35	3518	3515
Chirripó Grande 3	Caribbean	3514	3293	640	0.77	3389	3394
Fila Norte 1	Caribbean	3525	3248	1835	0.94	3460	3440
Fila Norte 2	Caribbean	3530	3354	870	0.19	3497	3499
Fila Norte 3	Caribbean	3491	3275	1040	0.31	3371	3377
Fila Norte 4	Caribbean	3576	3307	1730	0.98	3445	3439
Fila Norte 5	Caribbean	3500	3369	625	0.17	3390	3393

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713 Table 3

714 Parameters used to model paleo-glacier areas. Analytical Hillshading (AH),
715 Terrain Ruggedness Index (TRI) and Wind Exposition (WE). Null deviance is
716 36.78 on 30° df, residual deviance is 23.36 on 27° df, and the AIC is 89.18. Pr
717 ($> |z_j|$) is the probability of finding the observed Z-ratio in the normal
718 distribution of Z with a critical point of $|z_j|$. **P = 0.01, *P = 0.05.

Model terms	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)	
(Intercept)	18.206	5.019	3.627	0.001	**
AH	-0.128	0.427	-0.3	0.766	
TRI	-0.051	0.020	-2.494	0.019	*
WE	-12.847	4.044	-3.177	0.003	**

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